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IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component

PLC γ 2 In Vitro Solution Assay Using the Water Soluble C8CF3C Substrate

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Introduction

1-Phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2 (PLC γ 2, PLCG2) is an enzyme that converts PIP2 (phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate, PtdIns(4,5)P2, PI(4,5)P2) into IP3 (1D-myo-inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate) and diacylglycerol (DAG). PLC γ 2 is mainly expressed in immune cells and microglia, but only sparsely expressed in other brain cells such as astrocytes and oligodendrocytes.[1] A rare coding variant in PLC γ 2, Pro522Arg (P522R), was identified from an Alzheimer's disease genome-wide association study (GWAS)[2] and replicated in various populations.[3,4,5] This mutation was found to confer a protective effect where patients who carried this P522R mutation exhibited a slower rate of cognitive decline than patients who did not.[2] While the exact mechanism of this protective effect of the P522R PLC γ 2 mutant is not fully understood, this mutation does induce a slight increase in enzymatic activity.[1] Therefore, pharmacological intervention that increases the wild-type PLCG2's activity may provide a therapeutic strategy to lessen the cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease patients.

At the time of writing, published literature described only two molecules that activate phospholipase C (PLC) enzymes in vitro, U73122 (1-(6-((17 β -3-methoxyestra-1,3,5(10)-trien-17-yl)amino)hexyl)-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione) [7] and m-3M3FBS (2,4,6-trimethyl-N-(meta-3-trifluoromethyl-phenyl)-benzenesulfonamide) [8]. U73122 has been shown to activate PLC β and PLC γ family members in vitro [7], but it was originally identified as an inhibitor of PLCs.[9] In fact, U73122 was extensively used as the

prototypical inhibitor of PLC enzymes in cell culture.[10,11,12,13,14] However, more recently U73122 has also been shown to affect numerous other cellular proteins including phospholipase D [15], 5-lipoxygenase [16], calcium channels [17], potassium channels [18], telomerase [19], histamine H1 receptor [20], and sarco/endoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺-ATPase.[21] This complete lack of specificity is not surprising as the maleimide in U73122 can react with the thiol present in cysteine residues. Therefore, it is highly likely that U73122 non-specifically reacts with exposed cysteines on numerous proteins within a cell. This lack of specificity and high reactivity make U73122 a poor option to base a medicinal chemistry campaign with the goal of developing selective PLC γ 2 activators.

m-3M3FBS was originally identified from a screen of compounds that enhanced superoxide-generating activity in human neutrophils [8]. This activity was proposed to be caused by the direct activation of PLCs.[8] Supporting this proposition, several labs have shown that one downstream signaling effect of PLC activation—intracellular calcium release—was observed in various cell types treated with m-3M3FBS.[22,23,24,25,26] However, the potency and specificity of PLC activation of m-3M3FBS has been called into question, as there are reports that intracellular calcium release occurs before any PLC activity is detected,[27] and that m-3M3FBS effects the inward and outward flow of ions in a PLC-independent manner possibly through the direct inhibition of delayed rectifier potassium channels.[28] Additionally, m-3M3FBS has been shown to be cytotoxic in some cell lines.[23,24,25] Currently, it is unclear if m-3M3FBS exerts its activity primarily through PLC activation and if it does, whether a derivative could be identified that is selective for PLC γ 2.

As no selective small molecule activators of PLC γ 2 are currently known, there is a clear need to identify such an activator to determine whether the pharmacological activation of PLC γ 2 is a viable therapeutic strategy to treat Alzheimer's disease. Fortunately, there are enzymatic assays that have already been developed that are amenable for high-throughput screening (HTS).[29,30] These assays were primarily developed to identify inhibitors of PLC enzymes,[31] but these assays and substrates can be readily modified to screen for PLC γ 2 activators. These assays can be broadly classified into two groups. The first utilizes a water soluble substrate epitomized by WH-15 that measures the catalytic activity of PLC enzymes in solution,[29] while the second uses a hydrophobic substrate such as XY-69 that imbeds in a micelle or liposome to measure the activity of PLC enzymes at a surface interface that better mimics the natural membrane-bound substrate PIP₂ [30].

As reported in the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component PLC γ 2 Solution Substrate Synthesis – C8CF3C, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562001>, the TREAT-AD Center synthesized a WH-15 derivative with enhanced fluorescent properties. In this resource document, we detail the protocol of using this newly synthesized C8CF3C substrate to monitor the “solution” activity of PLC γ 2. This substrate and generalized protocol should be amenable to other phospholipase C enzymes as well.

General Protocol

General Procedures of PLCy2 Solution Assay Using C8CF3C

The PLCy2 solution assay with the C8CF3C substrate was prepared by modifying a previously reported phospholipase methodology for another phospholipase C substrate.[29] Full-length PLCy2 wild-type (WT) was expressed and purified by the Mesecar lab at Purdue University. Expression and purification conditions can be found in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562203>. Enzyme and substrate solution were prepared with HEPES assay buffer (HAB, 50 mM HEPES, 70 mM KCl, 3 mM CaCl₂, 3 mM EGTA, 2 mM DTT and 0.04 mg/ml of fatty acid-free BSA, pH 7.4). A general protocol for the determination of the enzymatic activity of PLCy2 is described below:

1. 1 μM of PLCy2 WT (20 mM HEPES, 150 NaCl, 5 %v/v glycerol, 1 mM DTT) was diluted with HAB (50 mM HEPES, 70 mM KCl, 3 mM CaCl₂, 3 mM EGTA, 2 mM DTT and 0.04 mg/ml of fatty acid free BSA, pH 7.4) to yield a final protein concentration of 0.5-8 nM.
2. 1 mM of C8CF3C in water was diluted with HAB (50 mM HEPES, 70 mM KCl, 3 mM CaCl₂, 3 mM EGTA, 2 mM DTT and 0.04 mg/ml of fatty acid free BSA, pH 7.4) to yield a substrate concentration of 8 μM .
3. 10 μL of PLCy2 WT (0-8 nM) and 10 μL of C8CF3C (8 μM) were plated in the wells of a black 384-well microtiter plate. The final concentrations of PLCy2 WT and C8CF3C are 0-4 nM and 4 μM , respectively in 20 μl of total volume.
4. The plate was placed on a plate reader and its fluorescence intensity (ex: 362 nm; em: 496 nm) was recorded every 2 min for 60 min.

Figure 1. Enzymatic reactions of PLCy2 WT (0-4 nM) with C8CF3C substrate (4 μM).

As shown in **Figure 1**, PLCy2 WT exhibits a dose-dependent increase in the rate of C8CF3C cleavage as expected.

Validation of PLCy2/C8CF3C Reaction in Solution Assay Using the PLCy2 inhibitor, ATP (adenosine triphosphate)

To validate the C8CF3C for enzymatic reactions of PLCy2 WT in the solution assay, ATP was utilized as an inhibitor. Various concentrations (0-100 mM) of ATP were prepared in water. PLCy2 WT (5 nM) and C8CF3C (8 μM) were prepared with HAB as described above. 1 μl of ATP solution (0-100 mM) and 10 μl PLCy2 WT (5 nM) was added to a

Figure 2. Titration of ATP for PLC γ 2/C8CF3C in solution assay. (A) Enzymatic reaction curves of PLC γ 2/C8CF3C in various concentrations of ATP and (B) Titration profile of ATP.

384-well plate and incubated for 15 min at room temperature. After incubation, 10 μ l of C8CF3C (8 μ M) was added. The final concentrations of ATP, PLC γ 2 WT and C8CF3C are 0-4.8 mM, 2.4 nM and 3.8 μ M, respectively in a total volume of 21 μ l. The fluorescence intensities from the enzymatic reactions were monitored with ex: 362 nm and em: 496 nm, as described above. The slope of reaction curves in the initial linear range (60 min) was used for analysis. As shown in **Figure 2**, ATP inhibited the enzymatic activity of PLC γ 2 WT in a dose-dependent manner with IC₅₀ of 11.05 μ M.

Kinetics Studies for C8CF3C Cleavage by PLC γ 2 in the Solution Assay.

To further characterize the C8CF3C substrate, the kinetic parameters of the cleavage of C8CF3C by PLC γ 2 were determined in the solution assay (**Figure 3**). PLC γ 2 WT (2 nM) and C8CF3C (0-200 μ M) were prepared with HAB as described above. 10 μ l of PLC γ 2 (2 nM) were added into the wells of a 384-well plate followed by a dispensing 10 μ l of the C8CF3C substrate (0-200 μ M). The final concentrations of PLC γ 2 WT and C8CF3C are 1.0 nM and 0-100 μ M, respectively in a total volume of 20 μ l. Fluorescence intensities from the enzymatic reactions were monitored with ex: 362 nm and em: 496 nm, as described above. The slope of the reaction curves in the initial linear range (30 min) was used for analysis.

The K_m of PLC γ 2 for C8CF3C was 28.6 ± 5.6 μ M with a V_{max} of 1.24 ± 0.42 pmol/min/ng for solution assay (**Figure 3**). These results suggest that the novel compound, C8CF3C, is feasible as a reporter substrate to determine the enzymatic activities of PLC γ 2.

Figure 3. Kinetic studies of C8CF3C and PLCy2. (A) Enzymatic reaction curves of PLCy2 with various concentrations of C8CF3C (μM) and (B) Michaelis- Menten plot for C8CF3C and PLCy2.

Application of the PLCy2 and C8CF3C Solution Assay for High Throughput Screening (Z'-score determination):

To establish the optimized solution assay conditions for C8CF3C and PLCy2 for high throughput screening, the Z' factor was determined in a pilot screen (**Figure 4**). In the screen, 0 nM, 2.5 nM, and 5 nM of PLCy2

Figure 4. Z' factor determination for HTS in a pilot screen. Blue color, enzyme control (1X protein concentration; red color, activation control (2X protein concentration); green color, inhibition control (No protein).

were used as inhibition, enzyme, and activation control, respectively. PLCy2 (0, 5 and 10 nM) and C8CF3C (8 μM) were prepared in HAB as mentioned above. 10 μl of PLCy2 enzyme concentrations of 0, 5, and 10 nM were added to the 384-well plate. The reaction was initiated by adding 10 μl of C8CF3C. The final concentrations of PLCy2 WT and C8CF3C are 0, 2.5, 5 nM and 4 μM , respectively in a total volume of 20 μl . Fluorescence intensities from the enzymatic reactions were monitored with ex: 362 nm and em: 496 nm, as described above.

The Z' scores for inhibition and activation were 0.727 and 0.077, respectively. These results suggest that the optimized solution assay of PLCy2 using the C8CF3C substrate is excellent for screening of inhibitors and feasible for the screening of activators.

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